

Approved by

Academic Council Resolution -Protocol - N10 June 27, 2025

LEPL Georgian State University of Sport

**4I GENDER EQUALITY PLAN (4I GEP)
FOR THE GEORGIAN STATE UNIVERSITY OF SPORT
2025–2028**

Introduction

Gender equality is a fundamental human right and the foundation for a peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable society. In the context of sports higher education system, promoting gender equality ensures that all students and academic and administrative staff, regardless of gender, have equal opportunities to participate, excel, and lead.

GSTUPES developed its initial Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in 2022, which is accessible on the university's website: <https://sportuni.ge/info/329/>. However, this GEP was not comprehensive enough to ensure the elimination of gender-based violence and harassment. In 2023, GSTUPES joined the "SUPPORTER" project. SUPPORTER, an EU-funded project - aims to assist eight sports higher education institutions across Central and Eastern Europe in developing their own intersectional, innovative, inclusive, and impactful Gender Equality Plans (4I -GEPs), which explicitly address gender-based violence and sexual harassment. More information is available at: <https://www.supporter-project.eu/>.

Our project involved the development of a roadmap, which then guided our grounding actions: For more information on the roadmap, please visit our website: <https://www.supporter-project.eu/roadmap-towards-the-development-of-a-4i-gep-gstupes/>

The core of SUPPORTER's work involves transforming existing GEPs into inclusive, innovative, intersectional, and impactful (4I-GEPs). In 2025, GSTUPES developed a new 4I GEP. This transformation was guided by tailored roadmaps co-created between each implementing organization (IO), including GSTUPES, and the project's core team. These strategic plans, developed between December 2023 and March 2024, are based on the specific needs of each institution and are designed to maximize impact, coordinate action, and manage risk.

While both the initial and the new 4I GEP aim to promote gender equality, they emphasize slightly different areas. While the first plan was concentrating on developing support to individuals facing discrimination, the new plan builds on the actions developed as part of the supporter project and aims to bring about structural changes: developing an inclusive organisation culture for gender equality in our sport university by addressing new topics such as work-life balance culture, preventing and tackling gender-based violence and integrating the gender dimension into research..

As highlighted by the SUPPORTER project, a key learning is the necessity of developing a 4I GEP. This new GEP is considered "4I" because it is:

Intersectional: The GEP recognizes the diverse and overlapping identities that individuals may have, such as gender, race, ethnicity, disability, and more. It includes actions like developing training programs that address multiple forms of discrimination and bias, conducting intersectional audits to identify and address gaps in existing policies, and ensuring that recruitment and promotion processes consider the intersectional identities of candidates.

Innovative: The GEP incorporates cutting-edge approaches to promote gender equality. For example, it introduces a digital platform for anonymous feedback and suggestions on gender equality initiatives, develops an interactive online course on recognizing and preventing gender-based violence and sexual harassment, and uses data analytics to identify and address gender imbalances in decision-making processes.

Inclusive: The GEP aims to create an environment where everyone, regardless of their background or identity, feels valued and supported. It includes actions like implementing flexible work arrangements to accommodate diverse needs, establishing family-friendly HR policies, and providing mentorship and leadership development programs that are accessible to individuals from diverse backgrounds.

Impactful: The GEP is designed to create meaningful and lasting change. It outlines strategic objectives, specific actions, timelines, responsible stakeholders, and indicators for measuring progress. Actions like establishing an independent body for handling gender-based violence and sexual harassment cases, setting and monitoring gender parity goals for leadership and academic positions, and developing a centralized dashboard to monitor progress, ensure that the plan is both comprehensive and effective.

This 4I Gender Equality Plan (GEP) affirms our university's commitment to fostering an inclusive, diverse, and equitable environment. It outlines strategic objectives, specific actions, timelines, responsible stakeholders, and indicators for measuring progress. The plan will be monitored and reviewed regularly to ensure relevance and responsiveness to evolving institutional and societal needs.

Vision and Mission

Vision: To become a national and regional leader in advancing gender equality in sports education and academia, empowering individuals to achieve their full potential.

Mission: To create an inclusive university culture that guarantees equal opportunities across all genders in sports education, leadership, research, and governance. GSTUPES is committed to addressing structural inequalities, preventing gender-based violence, and ensuring a supportive work-life balance.

Strategic Objectives and Action Plan

Goal	Measures and Activities	Timeline	Responsibility	Indicators
1. Foster Organizational Culture on Gender Equality (GE), Address Stereotypes and Biases	1.1. Organize at least once a year an event on Gender-based violence and sexual harassment. (roundtables, training, and public campaigns). 1.2. develop guidelines on GE topics (gender sensitive, inclusive language). 1.3. Conduct alumni and outreach events.	1.1 Every March 1.2. At the end of the academic year (June-August) 1.3. September 2026 1.4. February 2026	1.1. Gender Equality Committee, Communications Unit, SUPPORTER team 1.2. HR Department, Rectorate 1.3 a 1.4. Communications Unit,	1.1. Event reports, increase the learning of participants by 30 % 1.2. Two developed guidelines 1.3. Attendance statistics, at least 40% of men attending the event 1.4. Feedback surveys

	1.4.- Introduce a digital platform for anonymous feedback on gender inequalities and GBV and suggestions on gender equality initiatives.		SUPPORTER team	
2. Promote Work-Life Balance and Support for Caregivers	2.1. Implement flexible work arrangements (online, hybrid, remote) 2.2. Organise one to one session with people coming back from paternal leave.	2.1. December 2026 2.2. Will continue permanently from January 2026	2.1. Rector, Chancellor, HR Department 2.2. HR Department	2.1. One Flexible work policy adopted, Staff satisfaction surveys (once a year)/ 60 % of men and women people are satisfied 2.2 Satisfaction Survey related to one-on-one session / 70 % of men and women are satisfied
3. Prevent and Eliminate Gender-Based Violence (GBV), Sexual Harassment (SH), and Discrimination	3.1. Training of GE committee members in case management and confidentiality. 3.2. Conduct regular internal gender and intersectional audits to identify and address gaps in existing policies and practices related to GBV/SH	3.1. Launch Fall 2025, then Ongoing 3.2. Every December	3.1. HR department, GE experts, 3.2. Gender Equality Committee.	3.1. All members trained 3.2 Annual audit reports /40% of improvements of identified issues

<p>4. Achieve Gender Balance in Decision-Making</p>	<p>4.1. Set and monitor gender goals (target: 40/60) for leadership and academic positions. 4.2- Ensure that recruitment and promotion processes are inclusive and consider the intersectional identities of candidates. 4.3 Set and monitor gender parity goals (target: 40/60) for leadership and academic positions</p>	<p>4.1, 4.2, 4.3 - From Fall 2025</p>	<p>4.1, 4.2, 4.3 - Rector, Vice-Rector, HR Department, Faculty Management, SUPPORTER team</p>	<p>4.1, 4.2, 4.3 - Annual gender-disaggregated staff data 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 - Gender representation in management roles (after elections 60/40), Gender balance in candidate electoral lists (60/40)</p>
<p>5. Integrate Gender Dimension into Teaching and Research</p>	<p>5.1. Encourage gender-focused research in sports science 5.2. Facilitate student-led and international collaboration on GE themes.</p>	<p>5.1., .5.2 - Annually – from fall 2025</p>	<p>5.1, .5.2 - Vice rector, Research Office, Faculty Management,</p>	<p>5.1. Increased number of GE publications (<2 in year) 5.2 Student participation data, event reports(<5 students in year)</p>

<p>6. Gender+ Data Collection and Monitoring</p>	<p>6.1. Use findings to identify gaps and guide interventions. 6.2. Develop a centralized dashboard to monitor progress. 6.3 Collect and analyse data that is disaggregated by multiple social categories, such as gender, race, ethnicity, and disability. 6.4. Pilot round of Data Collection 6.5. Data Analysis</p>	<p>6.1. From Fall 2025 6.2. January 2026 6.3 Every June from 2026 6.4. December 2025 6.5. April 2026</p>	<p>6.1. SUPPORTER team, HR 6.2. SUPPORTER team, HR 6.3. SUPPORTER team, HR 6.4. SUPPORTER team, Research office 6.5. SUPPORTER team, Research office</p>	<p>6.1 Policy revisions based on data 6.2 Monitoring tools in use 6.3. Pilot data report 40 % of the respondents replied to the full survey 6.4. Number of respondents/participants - 50 % of the personnel replied to the full survey 6.5. Report on findings</p>
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Implementation and Review

The Gender Equality Committee, in collaboration with university leadership, will oversee implementation. Progress will be reviewed annually, with a mid-term evaluation in 2026. Updates will be communicated to the university community, and adjustments will be made in response to feedback, new data, or contextual changes.